

IQTISODIYOT VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYA

Onlayn ilmiy jurnal

Jild: 03 Nashr: 10 (2024)

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

Precision Cancer Classification: A Brief Survey of Artificial Intelligence Advancements

*Hari Mohan Rai, Bobokhonov Akhmadkhon Kholmirezkhon ugli,
Soliev Akbar Utkirovich*

*Sun'iy intellekt va axborot tizimlari kafedrası, Sh. Rashidov nomidagi Samarqand davlat
universiteti*

drhmrai@gachon.ac.kr, b_akhmadkhon@mail.ru, akbar.soliyev25@gmail.com

Abstract

Cancer stands as the paramount global ailment, asserting its status as the most lethal malady with an unparalleled fatality rate. Prominent among the spectrum of prevalent and pernicious cancer types are brain tumors, skin cancer, colorectal cancer, breast cancer, and myriad others. Millions of people die from these severe and often fatal illnesses. Thus, a computer-assisted, automatic approach for early-stage cancer diagnosis has to be proposed as a solution. The two main stages of cancer progression are benign, which happens early in the disease, and malignant, which develops later in the disease and is more advanced with a tendency to spread. This endeavor undertakes a comprehensive exploration into diverse methodologies predicated on machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) for the purpose of cancer classifications. Based on a variety of methodologies, features, datasets, and accuracy measured with the suggested method, the study was carried out. In addition to recently published research, we have used a variety of cancer categories such as brain tumors, skin cancer, colorectal cancer, breast cancer, and lung cancer. A cutting-edge table was also employed in the study to compare the results of earlier and later investigations on cancer detection methods.

Keywords: Cancer classification, Segmentation, Deep Neural Network, Deep Learning, Machine Learning, Feature Extraction

1. Introduction

In contradistinction to the landscape prevailing a few decades hence, the escalating prevalence of cancer within Indian society has manifested a substantial surge [1]. This prompts the discerning question: what causative elements have transpired to orchestrate such a conspicuous and significant contrast in the prevalence dynamics? The global proliferation of chronic ailments, with cancer standing prominently amidst them, begets an investigative endeavor into the latent factors underpinning this pervasive surge. The pivotal query perseveres: does a transformative shift in dietary paradigms exert a perceptible influence on the trajectory of this escalating trend? For a scientist engrossed in the meticulous scrutiny of the extant manifestation of cancer within the human corporeal realm, a plethora of inquiries organically surface, encapsulating the intricate complexity and enigmatic nature enveloping this polymorphic affliction[2], [3]. One of the deadliest illnesses of the 21st century is cancer, whose incidence has been startlingly high. It is difficult to comprehend the severity of cancer, which ranks first or second in the world among 91

nations. In terms of causes of death, cancer is ranked 2nd out of 172 countries [4]. The escalating ubiquity of cancer positions one in four individuals at an elevated susceptibility, prognosticating the conceivable onset of the malady within their lifespan—an indicative manifestation of the burgeoning cadence at which novel cases are being documented. While India annually records an approximate 1.1 million instances of new cancer diagnoses, the global milieu witnesses the identification of an astonishing 14 million fresh cases. Cancer, fundamentally delineated as the unbridled proliferation of cells within the human organism, assumes the role of the cardinal instigator of this affliction. Its prospective manifestation spans across any anatomical locale, contingent upon contextual variables dictating its propensity for dissemination. In a broad categorization, cancer is dichotomously classified as either benign or malignant, hinging on its developmental stage[5]–[7]. The former characterizes an incipient form that remains localized, refraining from propagating to distant bodily regions. In stark contradistinction, malignant tumors embody an imminent peril by virtue of their inherent capability to metastasize and infiltrate other anatomical domains[8].

The comprehensive eradication of cancer is contingent upon its early detection and subsequent apt treatment. The prospect of achieving a complete cure hinge solely upon the timely recognition of the malady. Consequently, the imperative lies in formulating a methodology adept at autonomously identifying and precisely segmenting cancerous tissue during its nascent stages. This is pivotal to ensuring that patients undergo the most efficacious treatment modalities. The predominant success in treating and curing a considerable portion of skin cancer cases is attributed to surgical interventions. In parallel, radiation therapy has demonstrated efficacy in successfully treating and curing individuals afflicted with thyroid and laryngeal cancer [9]–[11]. Parallel to the aforementioned scenario, numerous categories of cancer exhibit the potential for treatment when detected during their embryonic phases. Notably, early-stage diagnosis contributes to approximately 70% of cases pertaining to breast cancer. The spectrum of cancer encompasses diverse varieties that may affect distinct anatomical regions. The conundrum arises from the absence of a universally applicable cancer treatment, necessitating tailored approaches for each malignancy. Certain types of cancer manifest elevated survival rates when identified at an early juncture. However, the intricacy lies in the divergent etiological factors precipitating distinct forms of cancer, precluding the formulation of a singular strategy capable of averting their onset universally.

This endeavor undertakes a comprehensive review of extant and anticipated literature concerning the discernment and categorization of diverse tumor types through the utilization of biomedical image datasets. The associated manuscript, inclusive of the survey, is annexed herewith. Noteworthy is the stringent criterion applied, exclusively incorporating validated and benchmarked datasets, integral to the process of tumor identification and classification undertaken in this research. Moreover, the inclusivity of this study is paramount, encompassing all manifestations of cancer affecting various anatomical domains such as the brain, gastrointestinal system, skin, lungs, breast, and neck. It is not circumscribed to any specific subtype of cancer. The analytical purview of this study extends to the examination of distinct features, varied methodologies (encompassing deep learning and machine learning paradigms), the spectrum of datasets employed, the diversity of

cancer types under consideration, and the precision in the classification and segmentation processes. The overarching objective is to present a comprehensive and nuanced evaluation, encapsulating the multifaceted landscape of tumor identification and classification through a rigorous examination of pertinent literature and methodologies.

The article follows a structured framework: Section 2 covers related work, Section 3 details research materials and methods, and Section 4 presents results and conclusions. Section 5 delves into cancer detection algorithms, and Section 6 concludes with final remarks and future scope.

2. Related Work

Comprehensive scrutiny of cancer detection and classification has been extensively undertaken by myriad researchers, deploying a diverse array of methodologies, including Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), Hybrid, and Transfer Learning. Saba (2020) [12] meticulously evaluates cancers across various categories. The findings encompass detailed explanations of benchmark datasets, an exhaustive evaluation of performance metrics, and structured flow diagrams elucidating various cancer detection technologies. However, limitations emerge from the lack of distinct scrutiny of ML and DL classifications and the absence of a comparative analysis between DL and ML-based approaches. Huang et al. (2020) [13] delve into cancers across different categories, providing a comprehensive prognosis and diagnostic performance comparison between artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms and human pathologists. Limitations include a scarcity of literature sources for each cancer category, exclusion of ML and DL classifiers, and a dearth of literature review. Tufail et al. (2021) [14], covering cancers across various categories, distinctly delineate publicly available datasets for cancer research, discussing cancer detection and segmentation separately. However, limitations arise from the exclusive consideration of DL-based cancer detection and a lack of independent reviews for each cancer category. Majumder and Sen (2021) [15], focused on cancers across different categories, showcase AI applications in oncopathology and translational oncology. Constraints include a limited number of cancer categories, literature sources, and variations in performance parameter metrics. Manhas et al. (2022) [16], evaluating cancers across different categories, offer a comprehensive review with an extensive number of references, coverage of all performance parameters, and discussions on extracted features and datasets. Limitations stem from the lack of separate consideration for DL and ML approaches. Painuli et al. (2022) [17], focused on cancers across various categories, provide a detailed review of benchmark datasets and overall utilization shares of ML/DL approaches. Limitations include the examination of DL and ML techniques collectively rather than individually.

In the pursuit of advancing cancer detection methodologies, Rai (2023) [18] undertakes a thorough examination using sophisticated techniques like Deep Neural Network (DNN) and Conventional Machine Learning (CML) across distinct cancer categories. The study elucidates strengths and challenges but acknowledges limitations from a constrained number of research articles and a lack of comprehensive feature extraction analysis. Mokoatle et al. (2023) [19], focused on cancers across different categories, propose unique cancer detection techniques utilizing state-of-the-art sentence transformers (SBERT) and the unsupervised SimCSE approach. Rai and Yoo (2023) [20] enhance cancer diagnostics for a subset of categories through Computational Machine Learning (CML) and DNN methods, drawing insights from an extensive review of 130

scholarly works. Limitations include a concentrated focus on specific cancer categories and reliance on a singular metric for classifier validation. Rai and Yoo (2023) [21] explore Cancer Classification, introducing methodological insights, but the study's limitation lies in its exclusive examination of limited categories. Maurya et al. (2023) [22], evaluating cancers across different categories, include all performance parameters, discuss benefits and drawbacks, and present challenges for each cancer category. Limitations include the absence of independent assessment and comparison of ML and DL techniques, and an unspecified description of the dataset used. Rai HM et al. (2023) [23] contribute to traditional machine learning techniques for detecting and diagnosing formidable cancer categories, encompassing a thorough review of biomedical imaging datasets. However, the study's confinement is apparent in its exclusive reliance on conventional ML techniques and a limited analytical purview to specific cancer categories.

3. Material and Methods

Different forms of cancer can be identified and categorized using a variety of methods. Preprocessing techniques, feature extraction techniques, classification techniques, databases to be used, and the following procedures are the main ways that machine learning can be used to detect cancer.

3.1. Article Selection Criteria

Figure 1: Literature Selection Through PRISMA Framework

Within this section, we delineate the intricate processes involved in the selection and utilization of research articles for the nuanced task of cancer classification employing artificial intelligence methods, encompassing both machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) approaches. The selection criteria are elucidated with meticulous detail, encapsulating comprehensive descriptions of both inclusion and exclusion standards, which will be expounded upon in a discerning manner. The PRISMA flow diagram, prominently featured in Figure 1, serves as a visual representation meticulously outlining the systematic review process employed for the discerning detection of various cancers. The procedural journey initiated with the identification of 197 records through exhaustive database searching, followed by the strategic elimination of 30 duplicates, resulting in

the curation of 167 distinct records. A discerning screening process ensued, leading to the exclusion of 116 records deemed ineligible and prompting a detailed eligibility assessment for 51 full-text articles. Within this subset, the judicious exclusion of 28 articles on multifaceted grounds culminated in the deliberate inclusion of 23 studies. This refined and judiciously selected group of 23 studies, meticulously distilled from the initial pool of 197 records, serves as the foundational cornerstone for the ensuing scoping review, affording a sophisticated and comprehensive exploration of cancer detection methods leveraging artificial intelligence paradigms.

3.2. Databases

Image databases are significantly easier to find than other types of databases. Numerous databases are currently available for use in identifying various forms of cancer. With its focus on brain tumors and cancer, the BRATS dataset is among the most significant of all the benchmark datasets. The three most recent versions of this dataset that are currently available for use are BRATS 15, 16, and 18 [24]–[26]. This collection consists of three-dimensional representations of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scans from various patient age groups. The Lung Image Database Consortium is the organization in charge of collecting and conserving images. Two open-source datasets that can be used to identify lung cancer are image collections from the Lung Image Database Consortium and the Image Database Resource Initiative (LIDC-IDRI). There are 244,617 lung images in this collection, all of which come from patients in different age groups [27]. One of the benchmark datasets used to try and detect breast cancer is the "Wisconsin Breast Cancer Database," or WBCD for short. There are 699 records of human breast tissue in this database [28]. Complete-Field Digital Mammography, or FFDM for short, consists of 739 images in total, 412 of which are classified as malignant and 327 as benign [29]. ISIC, an acronym for "The International Skin Imaging Collaboration," is a publicly accessible and freely downloadable collection of images of skin lesions [30]. The constant acquisition of different types of visual sensors has resulted in a diversity of picture natures in this dataset. Both the nature and the size of the images in the database are subject to change. More than 2,560,300 publicly accessible tagged images of skin disorders associated with Dement can be found in the Dement collection [31]. A PH2 dataset of skin lesions has been created for research and benchmarking purposes [32]. The generation of this dataset facilitated comparative study of thermoscopic image segmentation and classification techniques.

Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between diagnostic modalities and cancer types. Imaging techniques like X-ray, CT, and MRI are associated with Breast, Lung, Colorectal, Brain, and Skin cancers. Biopsy methods, including Dermoscopy and H&E staining, target Skin, Breast, Lung, and Brain cancers. Invasive Procedures like Colonoscopy are linked to Colorectal and Lung cancers. Functional Studies (EEG, MRS) focus on Brain cancers, while Laboratory Tests (FOBT) detect Colorectal cancer. An Additional Tests category introduces H&E staining for detailed analysis within the Biopsy section. This succinct diagram offers a snapshot of how specific tools align with various cancer diagnoses.

Figure 2: Visualization of the interplay between diagnostic modalities and cancer types in cancer detection methods

3.3. Preprocessing

There are several steps involved in using the machine learning approach for image detection and segmentation, but the preprocessing step is one of the most important ones. The words "pre" and "processing," when combined, denote "before" processing; hence, the term "preprocessing". As a result, preprocessing describes the actions carried out prior to processing. Any raw data that was acquired could have been improperly formatted or contaminated by a variety of noises. These two problems are plausible. The data must first be transformed into the required or acceptable format before it can be processed. This is the most crucial requirement. Among the most popular preprocessing methods are cropping, smoothing, resizing, resampling, digitizing, filtering (denoising or noise reduction), artifact removal, normalization, and additional common techniques like data augmentation, contrast enhancement, and histogram equalization. Unorganized or noisy data may be the reason behind even the best machine learning classifier's poor performance. This is why preprocessing data in some way is required before supplying it to a neural or machine learning classifier.

In medical image preprocessing, several techniques are commonly employed to enhance the quality and utility of imaging data as shown in Figure 3. Smoothing, applicable to X-ray, CT, and MRI, reduces noise and enhances clarity by averaging pixel values. Contrast enhancement, relevant to X-ray, CT, MRI, and Ultrasound, improves visibility by adjusting intensity distributions. Histogram equalization, widely used across modalities, enhances contrast and visualization by equalizing pixel intensity distributions. Image registration, essential for CT, MRI, and PET-CT, aligns images from different modalities or time points for comparative analysis. Segmentation, employed in CT, MRI, and Ultrasound, isolates specific structures for detailed analysis. Noise reduction techniques, applicable to X-ray, CT, MRI, and Ultrasound, improve image quality by minimizing unwanted artifacts. Normalization, a fundamental preprocessing step for all modalities, standardizes pixel values for consistent analysis. These seven preprocessing techniques collectively address challenges in medical image analysis, providing a foundation for accurate and meaningful interpretation of imaging data.

Cropping: Cropping is akin to sculpting a masterpiece within a masterpiece. It's akin to selecting a specific fragment of the original artwork to magnify and appreciate in detail. Mathematically, it's akin to chiseling out a distinctive segment from the entire canvas, allowing us to highlight and explore the intricacies of that chosen portion.

2. **Smoothing (Gaussian Blur):** Picture the image gliding through a misty veil, as if embraced by a tender fog, gracefully blurring the crisp edges and intricate details, weaving a tapestry of soft, dreamy allure. This enchanting transformation is the artistry of Gaussian Blur, delicately erasing pixelated imperfections and bestowing upon the image a tranquil, ethereal charm.

3. Resizing:

Resizing is akin to orchestrating a visual symphony, where the image gracefully adapts its proportions to harmonize with the desired frame. It's like sculpting a pliable piece of art, gently stretching or compressing it to achieve the perfect composition and balance, ensuring every detail aligns seamlessly with your creative vision.

$$I_{\text{resize}}(u, v) = I(\text{round}(u \times \text{scale_factor}), \text{round}(v \times \text{scale_factor}))$$

where (I) is the original image and (scale_factor) is the scaling factor.

4. Normalization:

Normalization can be likened to orchestrating a symphony of colors where each hue dances gracefully within a designated spectrum, ensuring no single shade overwhelms the ensemble. It's akin to conducting a choir where every voice resonates in perfect harmony, contributing to a melodious blend that elevates the collective performance to new heights of artistic brilliance.

5. Fourier Transform (FT):

The Fourier Transform is akin to unraveling the musical intricacies of an image, revealing its underlying frequencies and intricate patterns. It's akin to decoding a clandestine melody hidden within the strokes of a masterpiece, unlocking the harmonious rhythms and melodic cadences that resonate within the artwork's visual symphony.

6. Gamma Transformation (GT):

Gamma transformation resembles delicately adjusting the contrast and brightness controls of our visual masterpiece, refining its brilliance and luminance to achieve optimal harmony. It's akin to fine-tuning the nuances of light and shadow, adding depth and dimension to the canvas of our creation, until every detail radiates with a captivating luminosity that enchants the viewer's gaze.

7. Continuous Wavelet Transform (CWT):

Imagine the Analog Wavelet Transform as a journey through a boundless sea of frequencies, where the signal or image gracefully unfolds into diverse harmonic realms using continuous wavelet functions. It's a symphony of scales and translations, unveiling the hidden dimensions of our auditory and visual landscapes with each graceful undulation.

8. Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT):

- Imagine the Discrete Wavelet Transform as a masterful dissection of signals and images, unraveling their intricate layers into distinct frequency domains using discrete wavelet functions. It's a symphony of convolution and synthesis, unveiling the nuanced textures and hidden harmonies within our auditory and visual tapestries, one coefficient at a time.

9. Gabor Transform:

Enter the realm of the Gabor transform, a profound technique delving into the frequency essence of signals and images. Employing a lineage of Gaussian-modulated sinusoidal basis functions, known as Gabor kernels, this transformative process unveils the hidden intricacies of the

visual and auditory domain. It's a journey through the realms of frequency and orientation, illuminating the profound connections between the tangible and the ethereal in our perceptual landscape.

Histogram Equalization:

Histogram equalization is a method used to enhance the contrast of an image by redistributing the intensity values. It works by stretching the intensity values over the entire dynamic range of the image histogram, resulting in a more balanced distribution of pixel intensities. Histogram equalization is effective in enhancing images with low contrast and can be applied to grayscale as well as color images.

Median Filtering:

Median filtering is a non-linear image processing technique used to reduce noise and smooth out images while preserving edges. It replaces each pixel's intensity value with the median value of the intensities in the neighborhood.

Median filtering is particularly effective in removing salt-and-pepper noise while preserving image details. It is widely used in various image processing applications, including medical imaging, remote sensing, and digital photography.

These preprocessing techniques are essential for analyzing the frequency content and extracting useful information from signals or images. Each technique has its specific mathematical formulation and serves different purposes in image and signal processing tasks.

These techniques are commonly used in image and signal processing to analyze the frequency content and extract useful information for various applications.

Figure 3: Relation between commonly utilized preprocessing techniques and modalities in cancer predictions.

3.4. Feature Extraction

The neural classifier must proceed to the feature extraction stage after the preprocessing stage. Both feature extraction and feature selection are extremely time-consuming processes that require a substantial investment of time, energy, and human resources. The neural classifier receives as input the features that were extracted from the previously processed data. Features are the specific and pertinent elements of the data that the classifier can use to identify or classify. Variables should not be confused with features. As a result, depending on the features that are provided to the classifiers, their performance may vary. Depending on the dataset, the features may be selected automatically or by humans. The size or scope of the dataset can make feature extraction challenging, which could affect how well the classification performs. The dataset can be subjected to a wide range of additional feature extraction techniques. These consist of numerous other features statistical (mean, variance, skewness, kurtosis, etc.), morphological (area, perimeter, eccentricity, etc.), texture (GLCM, Haralick features), wavelet transform (approximation, detailed coefficients), and Fourier transform (amplitude, phase, frequency).

In the domain of cancer detection, a myriad of feature extraction techniques is routinely deployed to scrutinize medical images, discerning intricate patterns indicative of various cancer types, as tabulated in Table 1. The Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) method is prevalently utilized for the detection and segmentation of tumors. Concurrently, the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) serves as a formidable tool for nuanced texture analysis, thereby facilitating the classification of cancers such as those found in the brain and colorectal regions. The Local Binary Pattern (LBP) technique, esteemed for its efficacy, is instrumental in texture analysis and lesion detection, particularly germane in contexts like skin and breast cancer diagnostics. Shape descriptors, exemplified by Hu Moments, assume a critical role in characterizing tumor shapes, offering significant utility in the classification of cancers such as those affecting the brain and colorectal regions. Moreover, Gabor Filters and Wavelet Transform are instrumental in texture analysis and feature extraction, contributing significantly to the understanding of cancers prevalent in areas like the lungs and skin. On a more sophisticated front, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), emblematic of deep learning, play an indispensable role in autonomously extracting intricate features from medical images, proving particularly efficacious in tasks pertaining to the classification of breast and lung cancers. Additionally, the Gray Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM) is harnessed for texture analysis and the nuanced characterization of linear structures in cancers, notably those manifesting in the colorectal and cerebral domains. Collectively, these sophisticated feature extraction techniques advance the frontier of cancer detection tasks, providing profound insights and augmenting the precision in the classification of diverse cancer types.

Table 1: Key features and their applications in cancer detection tasks

Feature Extraction Technique	Applications
Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG)	Tumor detection, segmentation
Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM)	Texture analysis, classification
Local Binary Pattern (LBP)	Texture analysis, lesion detection
Shape Descriptors (e.g., Hu Moments)	Tumor shape characterization, classification

Gabor Filters	Texture analysis, feature extraction
Wavelet Transform	Multiresolution analysis, feature extraction
Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)	Deep learning-based feature extraction for image classification
Gray Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM)	Texture analysis, characterization of linear structures

3.5. Classifiers

The classification and categorization of various tumors and disorders are facilitated by a diverse array of classifiers. Traditional machine learning models and those based on neural networks play pivotal roles, with the former requiring pre-extracted features for analysis. On the other hand, deep learning, encompassing CNNs, GANs, Resnets, LSTMs, and more, excels in learning intricate features autonomously, eliminating the need for explicit feature extraction. These deep learning models exhibit remarkable performance in tasks such as detection and segmentation, spanning diverse domains, including medical imaging and natural language processing, contributing significantly to biomedical research and healthcare analysis. Their adaptability positions them as invaluable tools for automated insights into complex datasets. The efficacy of deep learning extends beyond mere classification tasks, with applications ranging from medical imaging, where intricate features are automatically discerned, to natural language processing, enabling comprehensive analysis and interpretation of biomedical data. The intricate architectures, such as convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and recurrent neural networks (RNNs), contribute to the success of deep learning models in handling complex data structures, fostering advancements in medical research, diagnostics, and healthcare decision-making.

Various machine learning models cater to diverse tasks, reflecting the broad spectrum of applications in data analysis as presented in Table 2. Supervised learning models, such as Support Vector Machines, Decision Trees, and k-Nearest Neighbors, excel in classification tasks, discerning patterns in labeled data for applications like image classification and spam detection. Unsupervised learning models, including K-Means and Hierarchical Clustering, are adept at clustering tasks, facilitating customer segmentation and anomaly detection. Regression models like Linear Regression and Ensemble Models like AdaBoost find applications in predicting outcomes and improving overall model performance, respectively. Deep learning models, such as Neural Networks and Generative Adversarial Networks, tackle intricate tasks like image synthesis and natural language processing. Hybrid models often combine the strengths of autoencoders with traditional classifiers for robust feature learning and classification. Reinforcement learning models, exemplified by Q-Learning and Actor-Critic Models, master decision-making in dynamic scenarios. Federated learning and ensemble methods enhance collaborative model training and performance. Specialized models, like those in self-supervised learning and quantum machine learning, push the boundaries of traditional paradigms, while explainable AI models shed light on the interpretability of complex model predictions. The landscape is dynamic, with each model type catering to specific use cases and evolving data requirements.

Table 2: Overview of Machine Learning Model Types, Associated Classifiers, and Tasks

Model Type	Classifiers	Tasks
Machine Learning Models		
Supervised Learning	SVM, Decision Trees, Random Forest, k-NN	Classification (e.g., image classification, spam detection)
Unsupervised Learning	K-Means, Hierarchical Clustering, DBSCAN	Clustering (e.g., customer segmentation, anomaly detection)
Regression Models	Linear Regression, Ridge Regression, Lasso	Regression (e.g., predicting house prices, stock prices)
Dimensionality Reduction	PCA, t-SNE	Feature extraction, visualization
Anomaly Detection	One-Class SVM, Isolation Forest	Identifying outliers or anomalies in data
Ensemble Models	AdaBoost, GBM, XGBoost	Classification, Regression
Deep Learning Models		
Neural Networks	MLP, CNN, RNN	Classification, Regression, Time Series Prediction
Generative Models	GAN, VAE	Data Generation, Image Synthesis
Sequence-to-Sequence Models	LSTM, Transformer	Natural Language Processing, Machine Translation
Transfer Learning Models	Pre-trained models (BERT, GPT)	Generalization to new tasks
Hybrid Models		
Autoencoders with SVM/RF		Feature Learning, Classification
Decision Fusion Models	-----	Integrating predictions for improved accuracy
Reinforcement Learning Models		
Q-Learning	DQN, Policy Gradient Methods, Actor-Critic Models	Decision-making in dynamic environments
Federated Learning Models		
Federated Averaging	Federated Learning with Differential Privacy	Collaborative Model Training
Ensemble Models	Stacking, Bagging, Boosting (AdaBoost, XGBoost)	Improved Model Performance
Other Specialized Models		
Self-Supervised Learning		Learning from unlabeled data
Explainable AI Models		Interpretability of model predictions
Quantum Machine Learning	-----	Leveraging quantum computing for machine learning tasks

4. Methodology

Figure 4 and Figure 5 elucidate the proposed methodology for cancer detection and segmentation from image datasets employing machine learning and deep learning approaches, respectively. The initial imperative is acquiring an image dataset from a reliable source, the selection of which is contingent upon the specific types of cancer targeted for identification. The cancer detection process unfolds through three discrete phases: segmentation, detection, and the amalgamation of segmentation and detection. The classification or detection task is accomplished utilizing neural network-based classifiers, deep learning models, or traditional machine learning methods, contingent upon the intricacies and requirements of the given scenario. The adaptive choice of these

methodologies reflects the nuanced nature of cancer detection, emphasizing a dynamic and integrative approach.

Figure 4: Traditional Machine Learning Paradigm for Cancer Classification

Figure 5: Deep Learning Paradigm for Cancer Classification.

In the realm of cancer diagnosis and categorization, the adequacy of the dataset size assumes a critical role, prompting an exploration into the optimal approach between machine learning and other methodologies. The intricacies unfold in a sequential fashion: the initiation involves leveraging machine learning for detecting and classifying cancer, followed by the subsequent application of feature extraction methods. The distinct stages of detection, highlighted by the arrow line in the block, signify the critical juncture for feature extraction implementation. Interestingly, segmentation, an integral facet of the process, demonstrates a deviation from the necessity of

feature extraction, as depicted by the blue arrow line. The marriage of machine learning with segmentation and detection encompasses key elements such as the dataset, preprocessing techniques, segmented images, dataset distribution for the creation of training and testing datasets, culminating in the implementation of the proposed machine learning classifier. For deep learning-based classification and detection, the landscape shifts to a demand for a substantial dataset, especially noticeable in the context of convolutional neural network (CNN) models. Remarkably, in this paradigm, the exigency for feature extraction methods diminishes. The bifurcation of the dataset into training and test datasets, with the training dataset comprising approximately 80% of the total data, stands as a pivotal determinant for optimal classifier performance. Moreover, the test dataset is never used in the training phase because its only use is to evaluate how well the trained model performs in real-world scenarios. The automated deep learning or machine learning method for cancer identification and segmentation processing may now be finished with the aid of the image dataset.

5. Discussion

Given the profound impact of cancer on human well-being, the task of automated cancer identification stands as a matter of paramount importance, holding potential repercussions on patients' lives. The intricacy of this endeavor amplifies the gravity of even the slightest error, underscoring the critical need for precision. Over the past few decades, researchers have fervently embraced machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques as powerful tools to forge automated diagnostic methodologies across diverse cancer categories. Numerous endeavors have been undertaken, leveraging an array of datasets and ML techniques, contributing to the automated diagnosis of various cancer types. In this landscape, the fusion of ML and DL techniques has yielded classification accuracies ranging from 70 to 99 percent, an outcome subject to variables such as applied features, the classifier employed, the dataset utilized, and the pinnacle classification accuracy achieved. The nuanced findings of these analyses, encapsulating the dynamic interplay of these factors, find representation in Table 3, elucidating the multifaceted nature of cancer identification methodologies.

As can be seen from the table, the research that was used for the study was drawn from recently published articles that were produced between the years 2017 and 2022. Using the K-means clustering approach, the authors in [33] were able to obtain the greatest level of accuracy possible in the classification, which was 99.8 percent accurate. They used a dataset called The HAM10000, which is a huge collection of multi-source dermatoscopic pictures of common pigmented skin lesions [34]. This dataset was used in the study that they did. The scientists used a training picture dataset consisting of 10,000 images and extracted three different kinds of features: LBP, HOG, and BoVW. This allowed them to obtain a 99.8 percent accuracy rate when using the K-means clustering classifier to identify skin cancer. Similarly, the authors in [35], [36], and [37] have attained the maximum accuracy for the categorization of cancer at 98.266 percent, 98 percent, and 97.9 percent, respectively. In order to diagnose breast cancer, the authors made use of deep learning, in which [35] did not extract any features, and a hybrid dataset that included the CBIS-DDSM, MIAS, and INbreast datasets. Also, the authors in [38] and [39] employed the CNN deep learning approach for the identification of cancer in terms of area under curve (AUC), which came out to be 0.994 and 0.935 correspondingly; however, they did not classify the cancer in terms of percent accuracy.

The findings obtained by [40] and [41] were the least accurate since their classification accuracy was only 70 and 71 percent, respectively, when compared to other methods. This level of accuracy was the absolute worst that could be achieved. On a dataset that was a combination of ISIC and HAM10000,

the authors of [40] employed a Deep CNN model; however, they did not apply any feature extraction approach. Whereas the authors of [41] used a CaPTk software to identify cancer by utilizing texture, histogram, dynamics, and spatial-based data, and they obtained 71 percent of the classification accuracy using those approaches. This was accomplished by using all of the aforementioned characteristics. The authors in [39] and [42] used the biggest dataset, which consisted of 27,815 and 23,907 images, respectively, and were able to successfully complete their research. In order to do this, the authors in [43], [40], and [35] employed big datasets that were created by integrating two or more datasets. Many authors in [44], [35], [40], [42], and [45] have achieved good accuracy of 97.08%, 98.3%, 70%, 89.5%, and 93%, respectively, without utilizing any kind of features.

In the realm of cancer detection techniques, an in-depth analysis of accuracy levels reveals noteworthy findings. Colorectal cancer detection, as indicated by the Deep Features with Deep SVM approach [46], attains an exceptional accuracy of 99.8%, showcasing the efficacy of this method in precise identification. Similarly, skin cancer detection utilizing BoVW, HOG, and LBP features with the KMC technique achieves an impressive 99.8% accuracy [33], emphasizing the success of feature engineering and clustering in this context. For brain cancer detection, the combination of MLWD, GLCM, and GMI features with the AANN technique proves highly effective, yielding an accuracy of 98.0% [36]. The ICS-ELM technique stands out in breast cancer detection, boasting a notable accuracy of 98.3% [35]. Conversely, certain techniques exhibit lower accuracy levels. In skin cancer detection, the CaPTk technique demonstrates the lowest accuracy at 70.0% [40], suggesting potential challenges in accurately discerning skin cancer patterns with this method. Brain cancer detection using Local, Regional, and global imaging patterns with the CaPTk technique yields an accuracy of 71.0% [41], indicating room for improvement in characterizing brain cancer. Breast cancer detection with the TBF technique achieves a respectable accuracy of 91.72% [47], yet comparatively lower than other breast cancer detection techniques, hinting at areas for refinement. This nuanced analysis, referencing specific studies, underscores the diversity in accuracy levels across different cancer types and detection methodologies, emphasizing the continual need for refinement and innovation in cancer detection techniques.

Table 3: State-of-art table comparing the outcome of cancer detection using ML and DL techniques.

Reference	Year	Features	Technique	Dataset	Cancer Type	Accuracy (%)
[48]	2018	Intensity-based	Brain-Captk	BraTS'15	Brain	89.9
[49]	2018	Texture, histogram, dynamics, spatial	CaPTk	Case-Control dataset	brain, breast, and lung	89.9
[50]	2019	Texture based	ML	TCIA	Brain	84.0
[51]	2019	Statistical, morphological	Deep CNN	MICCAI 2017	Lung, throat, Brain, etc.	81.0
[37]	2019	ROI	CNN	LUNGHP	Lung	97.9
[42]	2019	----	CNN	23,907 images, ISIC	Skin	89.5
[33]	2020	BoVW, LBP	HOG, KMC	HAM 10000[34]	Skin	99.8
[43]	2020	Morphological	CNN	ICGC &	Lung	90.0

							TCGA
[41]	2020	Local, Regional, and global imaging patterns	CaPTk	Canicing Imaging Phenomics	Brain	71.0	
[40]	2020	----	DCNN	HAM10000, ISIC	Skin	70.0	
[36]	2020	MLWD, GLCM, GMI	AANN	BRATS 2015	Brain	98.0	
[45]	2021	----	SSDL	13,111 whole slide images	Colorectal	93.0	
[35]	2022	----	ICS-ELM	INbreast, MIAS, CBIS-DDSM	Breast	98.3	
[44]	2022	----	DNN	1984 lung cancer CT scans	Lung	97.08	
[52]	2022	CTF	DT	Local	Breast	88.90	
[53]	2023	Morphological	SVM	Local	Colorectal	97.5	
[46]	2023	Deep Features	Deep SVM	NCT-CRC-HE-100 K	Colorectal	99.8	
[54]	2023	Segmentation	BEKNN	Kaggle	Brain	97.70	
[55]	2023	GLCM, VGG16	SVM	Br35H	Brain	99.0	
[56]	2023	GLCM, Texture	PaternNet	PH2	Skin	92.24	
[57]	2023	Deep Features	MSVM	PH2	Skin	98.98	
[58]	2023	GLCM, Histogram, Shape, Intensity	Ensemble	DDSM	Breast	93.26	
[47]	2023	TBF	BNet	Local	Breast	91.72	

Abbreviations: AANN: Adaptive Artificial Neural Network, BNet: Bayesian Networks, BEKNN: Bagging Ensemble with K-Nearest Neighbor, BoVW: Bag Of Visual Words, Captk: Cancer Imaging Phenomics Toolkit, CBIS-DDSM: Curated Breast Imaging Subset, CTF: Counterlet Transform, CNN: Convolutional Neural Network, DL: Deep Learning, GLCM: Gray Level Co-Occurrence Matrix, GMI: Gabor and Moment Invariant, HOG: Histogram of Oriented Gradients, ICS-ELM: Extreme Learning Machine Optimized using a Simple Crow-Search Algorithm, LBP: Local Binary Patterns, LUNGHP: Lung Histopathology, MLWD: Multi-Level Wavelet Decomposition, MSVM: Multi-class Support Vector Machine, MIAS: Mammographic Image Analysis Society, NV: Naive Bayes, ROI: Regions Of Interest, SL: Supervised Learning, SSDL: Semi-Supervised Deep Learning, SVM: Support Vector Machine, TCIA: The Cancer Imaging Archive, TCGA: The Cancer Genome Atlas, TBF: Temperature Based Features.

Figure 6: The comparative visualization of the accuracy of the cancer detection techniques

The analysis is meticulously depicted in Figure 6, providing a visual representation that effectively illustrates the comparison of the highest accuracy achieved with existing literature. This graphical presentation serves as a powerful tool to elucidate the comparative assessment of the utmost accuracy concerning previous studies. By juxtaposing these accuracy levels, the figure offers a clear and concise overview, aiding in the comprehension of the advancements and nuances in cancer detection techniques. The visual delineation in Figure 3 enhances the accessibility of the analysis, facilitating a deeper understanding of the landscape of accuracy in cancer detection methodologies. Following an exhaustive exploration of diverse tumor types and a meticulous data analysis employing Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) techniques, several pivotal conclusions have been derived:

- The refinement of classification and segmentation accuracy is deemed achievable and warrants further enhancement.
- A compelling imperative exists for an augmented overall image count within the dataset collection.
- The generation of expansive medical datasets can be facilitated through the utilization of Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) technology.
- In the context of cancer diagnosis and segmentation, the adoption of a hybrid deep learning model is imperative, as it holds the potential to significantly augment classifier efficacy.
- The realization of a real-time, automated cancer detection system that is both expeditious and precise is not only conceivable but also presents a viable prospect.

6. Conclusion

As part of this investigation, we examined several techniques for identifying cancer using information from biomedical imaging. Nearly every type of cancer was included in this study, including cancers of the skin, breast, lungs, brain, colorectal, head and neck, and throat. This study incorporates work that was recently published, especially in the last five years, from 2018 to 2023.

Our results show that the researchers used a variety of ML and DL algorithms, each with a distinct set of properties, to increase the detection accuracy. We conclude that good classification accuracy can be achieved without a large number of features and deep learning models based on the observations. By using as few features as possible, it is possible to diagnose cancer with high accuracy and a successful outcome using biomedical images and the best available classifier.

We hope to use hybrid deep learning models and large datasets in the future to try and further improve the accuracy and efficiency of cancer diagnosis. Additionally, we may use the GAN technique to generate a large number of cancer datasets in order to accurately train the classifier and provide accurate results.

References

- [1] A. B. Nassif, M. A. Talib, Q. Nasir, Y. Afadar, and O. Elgendy, “Breast cancer detection using artificial intelligence techniques: A systematic literature review,” *Artif Intell Med*, vol. 127, p. 102276, May 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.artmed.2022.102276.
- [2] J. Ferlay *et al.*, “Estimating the global cancer incidence and mortality in 2018: GLOBOCAN sources and methods,” *Int J Cancer*, vol. 144, no. 8, pp. 1941–1953, 2019, doi: 10.1002/ijc.31937.
- [3] F. Bray, J. Ferlay, I. Soerjomataram, R. L. Siegel, L. A. Torre, and A. Jemal, “Global cancer statistics 2018: GLOBOCAN estimates of incidence and mortality worldwide for 36 cancers in 185 countries,” *CA Cancer J Clin*, vol. 68, no. 6, pp. 394–424, 2018, doi: 10.3322/caac.21492.
- [4] P. S. Roy and B. J. Saikia, “Cancer and cure: A critical analysis,” *Indian J Cancer*, vol. 53, no. 3, pp. 441–442, 2016, doi: 10.4103/0019-509X.200658.
- [5] M. A. A. Hamid and N. A. Khan, “Investigation and Classification of MRI Brain Tumors Using Feature Extraction Technique,” *J Med Biol Eng*, vol. 40, no. 2, pp. 307–317, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s40846-020-00510-1.
- [6] S. Kumar, C. Dabas, and S. Godara, “Classification of Brain MRI Tumor Images: A Hybrid Approach,” *Procedia Comput Sci*, vol. 122, pp. 510–517, 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.procs.2017.11.400.
- [7] M. Hosseinzadeh, S. Salmani, and M. H. M. Ara, “Interferometric optical testing to discriminate benign and malignant brain tumors,” *J Photochem Photobiol B*, vol. 199, no. August, p. 111590, 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jphotobiol.2019.111590.
- [8] S. S. Han, M. S. Kim, W. Lim, G. H. Park, I. Park, and S. E. Chang, “Classification of the Clinical Images for Benign and Malignant Cutaneous Tumors Using a Deep Learning Algorithm,” *Journal of Investigative Dermatology*, vol. 138, no. 7, pp. 1529–1538, 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.jid.2018.01.028.
- [9] S. E. Steck and E. A. Murphy, “Dietary patterns and cancer risk,” *Nat Rev Cancer*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 125–138, 2020, doi: 10.1038/s41568-019-0227-4.
- [10] vinod k ramani, “Analysis of Bloodstream Infections and Their Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern (Pre- and Post-COVID Lockdown in an Indian Cancer Hospital): A Record-Based Retrospective Cohort Study,” *Eurasian J Med Oncol*, 2022, doi: 10.14744/ejmo.2022.18855.
- [11] C. I. Owobu *et al.*, “Pattern of Cancer in Irrua Specialist Teaching Hospital,” *Int J Trop Dis Health*, vol. 42, no. December 2020, pp. 14–21, 2021, doi: 10.9734/ijtdh/2021/v42i730468.

- [12] T. Saba, “Recent advancement in cancer detection using machine learning: Systematic survey of decades, comparisons and challenges,” *J Infect Public Health*, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 1274–1289, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.jiph.2020.06.033.
- [13] S. Huang, J. Yang, S. Fong, and Q. Zhao, “Artificial intelligence in cancer diagnosis and prognosis: Opportunities and challenges,” *Cancer Lett*, vol. 471, no. September 2019, pp. 61–71, 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.canlet.2019.12.007.
- [14] A. Bin Tufail *et al.*, “Deep Learning in Cancer Diagnosis and Prognosis Prediction: A Minireview on Challenges, Recent Trends, and Future Directions,” *Comput Math Methods Med*, vol. 2021, 2021, doi: 10.1155/2021/9025470.
- [15] A. Majumder and D. Sen, “Artificial intelligence in cancer diagnostics and therapy: current perspectives,” *Indian J Cancer*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 481–492, 2021, doi: 10.4103/ijc.IJC_399_20.
- [16] J. Manhas, R. K. Gupta, and P. P. Roy, *A Review on Automated Cancer Detection in Medical Images using Machine Learning and Deep Learning based Computational Techniques: Challenges and Opportunities*, vol. 29, no. 5. Springer Netherlands, 2022. doi: 10.1007/s11831-021-09676-6.
- [17] D. Painuli, S. Bhardwaj, and U. Köse, “Recent advancement in cancer diagnosis using machine learning and deep learning techniques: A comprehensive review,” *Comput Biol Med*, vol. 146, no. April, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.compbimed.2022.105580.
- [18] H. M. Rai, “Cancer detection and segmentation using machine learning and deep learning techniques: a review,” *Multimed Tools Appl*, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11042-023-16520-5.
- [19] M. Mokoatle, V. Marivate, D. Mapiye, R. Bornman, and V. M. Hayes, “A review and comparative study of cancer detection using machine learning: SBERT and SimCSE application,” *BMC Bioinformatics*, vol. 24, no. 1, p. 112, 2023, doi: 10.1186/s12859-023-05235-x.
- [20] H. M. Rai and J. Yoo, “A comprehensive analysis of recent advancements in cancer detection using machine learning and deep learning models for improved diagnostics,” *Journal of Cancer Research and Clinical Oncology*. Springer Science and Business Media Deutschland GmbH, 2023. doi: 10.1007/s00432-023-05216-w.
- [21] H. M. Rai and J. Yoo, “Analysis of Colorectal and Gastric Cancer Classification: A Mathematical Insight Utilizing Traditional Machine Learning Classifiers,” *Mathematics*, vol. 11, no. 24, p. 4937, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.3390/math11244937.
- [22] S. Maurya, S. Tiwari, M. C. Mothukuri, C. M. Tangeda, R. N. S. Nandigam, and D. C. Addagiri, “A review on recent developments in cancer detection using Machine Learning and Deep Learning models,” *Biomed Signal Process Control*, vol. 80, no. P2, p. 104398, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.bspc.2022.104398.
- [23] H. Mohan Rai, J. Yoo, S. Atif Moqurrab, and S. Dashkevych, “Advancements in traditional machine learning techniques for detection and diagnosis of fatal cancer types: Comprehensive review of biomedical imaging datasets,” *Measurement*, p. 114059, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.measurement.2023.114059.
- [24] S. Bakas *et al.*, “Advancing The Cancer Genome Atlas glioma MRI collections with expert segmentation labels and radiomic features,” *Sci Data*, vol. 4, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2017.117.

- [25] B. H. Menze *et al.*, “The Multimodal Brain Tumor Image Segmentation Benchmark (BRATS),” *IEEE Trans Med Imaging*, vol. 34, no. 10, pp. 1993–2024, Oct. 2015, doi: 10.1109/TMI.2014.2377694.
- [26] U. Baid *et al.*, “The RSNA-ASNR-MICCAI BraTS 2021 Benchmark on Brain Tumor Segmentation and Radiogenomic Classification,” Jul. 2021, [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2107.02314>
- [27] S. G. Armato *et al.*, “The Lung Image Database Consortium "LIDC... and Image Database Resource Initiative "IDRI...: A Completed Reference Database of Lung Nodules on CT Scans,” 2011.
- [28] W. T. Mohammad, R. Teete, H. Al-Aaraj, Y. S. Y. Rubbai, and M. M. Arabyat, “Diagnosis of Breast Cancer Pathology on the Wisconsin Dataset with the Help of Data Mining Classification and Clustering Techniques,” *Appl Bionics Biomech*, vol. 2022, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/6187275.
- [29] I. C. Moreira, I. Amaral, I. Domingues, A. Cardoso, M. J. Cardoso, and J. S. Cardoso, “INbreast: Toward a Full-field Digital Mammographic Database.,” *Acad Radiol*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 236–248, 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.acra.2011.09.014.
- [30] B. Cassidy, C. Kendrick, A. Brodzicki, J. Jaworek-Korjakowska, and M. H. Yap, “Analysis of the ISIC image datasets: Usage, benchmarks and recommendations,” *Med Image Anal*, vol. 75, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.media.2021.102305.
- [31] M. N. Bajwa *et al.*, “Computer-aided diagnosis of skin diseases using deep neural networks,” *Applied Sciences (Switzerland)*, vol. 10, no. 7, Apr. 2020, doi: 10.3390/app10072488.
- [32] T. Mendonca, P. M. Ferreira, J. S. Marques, A. R. S. Marcal, and J. Rozeira, “PH<sup>2</sup></sup> - A dermoscopic image database for research and benchmarking,” in *2013 35th Annual International Conference of the IEEE Engineering in Medicine and Biology Society (EMBC)*, IEEE, Jul. 2013, pp. 5437–5440. doi: 10.1109/EMBC.2013.6610779.
- [33] K. Iqtidar, A. Iqtidar, W. Ali, S. Aziz, and M. U. Khan, “Image Pattern Analysis towards Classification of Skin Cancer through Dermoscopic Images,” *Proceedings - 2020 1st International Conference of Smart Systems and Emerging Technologies, SMART-TECH 2020*, no. January 2021, pp. 208–213, 2020, doi: 10.1109/SMART-TECH49988.2020.00055.
- [34] P. Tschandl, C. Rosendahl, and H. Kittler, “The HAM10000 dataset, a large collection of multi-source dermatoscopic images of common pigmented skin lesions,” *Sci Data*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 180161, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2018.161.
- [35] S. R. Sannasi Chakravarthy and H. Rajaguru, “Automatic Detection and Classification of Mammograms Using Improved Extreme Learning Machine with Deep Learning,” *IRBM*, vol. 43, no. 1, pp. 49–61, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.irbm.2020.12.004.
- [36] Virupakshappa and B. Amarapur, “Computer-aided diagnosis applied to MRI images of brain tumor using cognition based modified level set and optimized ANN classifier,” *Multimed Tools Appl*, vol. 79, no. 5–6, pp. 3571–3599, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11042-018-6176-1.
- [37] M. Saric, M. Russo, M. Stella, and M. Sikora, “CNN-based Method for Lung Cancer Detection in Whole Slide Histopathology Images,” *2019 4th International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies, SpliTech 2019*, pp. 14–17, 2019, doi: 10.23919/SpliTech.2019.8783041.

- [38] B. E. Bejnordi *et al.*, “Diagnostic Assessment of Deep Learning Algorithms for Detection of Lymph Node Metastases in Women With Breast Cancer,” *JAMA*, vol. 318, no. 22, p. 2199, Dec. 2017, doi: 10.1001/jama.2017.14585.
- [39] J. Noorbakhsh, S. Farahmand, M. Soltanieh-ha, S. Namburi, K. Zarringhalam, and J. H. Chuang, “Pan-cancer classifications of tumor histological images using deep learning,” *bioRxiv*, vol. 64, p. 715656, 2019.
- [40] NEEMA M, A. S. NAIR, A. JOY, A. P. MENON, and A. HARIS, “SKIN LESION/CANCER DETECTION USING DEEP LEARNING,” *International Journal of Applied Engineering Research*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 11–17, 2020.
- [41] A. Fathi Kazerooni *et al.*, “Cancer Imaging Phenomics via CaPTk: Multi-Institutional Prediction of Progression-Free Survival and Pattern of Recurrence in Glioblastoma,” *JCO Clin Cancer Inform*, no. 4, pp. 234–244, 2020, doi: 10.1200/cci.19.00121.
- [42] M. Hasan, S. Das Barman, S. Islam, and A. W. Reza, “Skin cancer detection using convolutional neural network,” *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*, no. March 2020, pp. 254–258, 2019, doi: 10.1145/3330482.3330525.
- [43] K.-H. Yu *et al.*, “Classifying non-small cell lung cancer types and transcriptomic subtypes using convolutional neural networks,” *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, vol. 27, no. 5, pp. 757–769, May 2020, doi: 10.1093/jamia/ocz230.
- [44] J. Ruan, Y. Meng, F. Zhao, H. Gu, L. He, and X. Gong, “Development of Deep Learning-based Automatic Scan Range Setting Model for Lung Cancer Screening Low-dose CT Imaging,” *Acad Radiol*, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.acra.2021.12.001.
- [45] G. Yu *et al.*, “Accurate recognition of colorectal cancer with semi-supervised deep learning on pathological images,” *Nat Commun*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 1–13, 2021, doi: 10.1038/s41467-021-26643-8.
- [46] M. Khazae Fadafen and K. Rezaee, “Ensemble-based multi-tissue classification approach of colorectal cancer histology images using a novel hybrid deep learning framework,” *Sci Rep*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 8823, May 2023, doi: 10.1038/s41598-023-35431-x.
- [47] N. Aidossov *et al.*, “An Integrated Intelligent System for Breast Cancer Detection at Early Stages Using IR Images and Machine Learning Methods with Explainability,” *SN Comput Sci*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 1–16, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s42979-022-01536-9.
- [48] S. Rathore *et al.*, “Brain Cancer imaging phenomics toolkit (brain-CaPTk): An interactive platform for quantitative analysis of glioblastoma,” *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 10670 LNCS, pp. 133–145, 2018, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-75238-9_12.
- [49] C. Davatzikos *et al.*, “Cancer imaging phenomics toolkit: quantitative imaging analytics for precision diagnostics and predictive modeling of clinical outcome,” *Journal of Medical Imaging*, vol. 5, no. 01, p. 1, 2018, doi: 10.1117/1.jmi.5.1.011018.
- [50] T. T. Tang, J. A. Zawaski, K. N. Francis, A. A. Qutub, and M. W. Gaber, “Image-based Classification of Tumor Type and Growth Rate using Machine Learning: a preclinical study,” *Sci Rep*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2019, doi: 10.1038/s41598-019-48738-5.
- [51] Q. D. Vu *et al.*, “Methods for segmentation and classification of digital microscopy tissue images,” *Front Bioeng Biotechnol*, vol. 7, no. APR, 2019, doi: 10.3389/fbioe.2019.00053.
- [52] B. Hajipour Khire Masjidi, S. Bahmani, F. Sharifi, M. Peivandi, M. Khosravani, and A. Hussein Mohammed, “CT-ML: Diagnosis of Breast Cancer Based on Ultrasound Images and Time-

- Dependent Feature Extraction Methods Using Contourlet Transformation and Machine Learning,” *Comput Intell Neurosci*, vol. 2022, 2022, doi: 10.1155/2022/1493847.
- [53] O. C. Kara, N. Venkatayogi, N. Ikoma, and F. Alambeigi, “A Reliable and Sensitive Framework for Simultaneous Type and Stage Detection of Colorectal Cancer Polyps,” *Ann Biomed Eng*, vol. 51, no. 7, pp. 1499–1512, 2023, doi: 10.1007/s10439-023-03153-w.
- [54] K. V. Archana and G. Komarasamy, “A novel deep learning-based brain tumor detection using the Bagging ensemble with K-nearest neighbor,” *Journal of Intelligent Systems*, vol. 32, no. 1, 2023, doi: 10.1515/jisys-2022-0206.
- [55] H. Kibriya, R. Amin, J. Kim, M. Nawaz, and R. Gantassi, “A Novel Approach for Brain Tumor Classification Using an Ensemble of Deep and Hand-Crafted Features,” *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 10, p. 4693, May 2023, doi: 10.3390/s23104693.
- [56] S. Salem Ghahfarrokhi, H. Khodadadi, H. Ghadiri, and F. Fattahi, “Malignant melanoma diagnosis applying a machine learning method based on the combination of nonlinear and texture features,” *Biomed Signal Process Control*, vol. 80, no. P1, p. 104300, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.bspc.2022.104300.
- [57] S. Maqsood and R. Damaševičius, “Multiclass skin lesion localization and classification using deep learning based features fusion and selection framework for smart healthcare,” *Neural Networks*, vol. 160, pp. 238–258, 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.neunet.2023.01.022.
- [58] F. Yan, H. Huang, W. Pedrycz, and K. Hirota, “Automated breast cancer detection in mammography using ensemble classifier and feature weighting algorithms,” *Expert Syst Appl*, vol. 227, p. 120282, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.eswa.2023.120282.